

APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT POPULAR STYLES IN FURNITURE DESIGN

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Abstract. *This article discusses popular historical and modern styles of furniture, as well as the material used and the description of the appearance of the furniture.*

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When talking about styles of furniture, most often they mean their inextricable connection with styles in furniture. But in the entire history of mankind, there are hardly more than a dozen architectural and furniture styles. Previously, furniture was decorated with decor, which was made from mahogany, ebony, in most cases it was done by hand.

The meaning of style according to Dahl's dictionary is an image, a taste. Style in our understanding is artistic unity. Each era has its own ideas. About the surrounding world, his vision of beauty and harmony, which is defined as style of a given era, but over time, the style changes with a new set and is created modernized style. Furniture style is a reflection of the culture embodied in furniture.

There are such types of antique style:

- antique;
- Romanesque;
- gothic;
- baroque;
- Empire;
- Provence.

There are some more types, but they are less popular and are not used as often, they are less likely to be found on sale, less often the craftsmen who make furniture hear about them. Now let's look at each type in detail.

Antique decoration is carried out based on the motives of Ancient Greece and Ancient Rome – columns, tiled marble floor, a lot of light. In such rooms you can find ornaments in spirals, leaves. Antique-style furniture, as a rule, is not sheathed, has a simple shape, is smooth to the touch and wooden with inlay in the form of a mosaic of expensive wood.

Cabinets in this style were not used – instead of them there were chests. The room should have additional accessories - cabinets, chests, low benches.

Romanesque for European furniture is about the same as Latin for all European languages. This style became the proto-language, which subsequently spoke furniture makers from almost all of Europe and the whole world.

It originated between 800 AD. and the beginning of the second millennium, after the decline of the Roman Empire, in the church architecture of southern France, becoming the result of the development and creative processing of Roman monuments, the heritage of Byzantine culture, as well as the culture of the Franks, Normans, Scandinavians.

As a rule, Romanesque furniture has a simple design and a rough massive shape. Cabinets made of poorly planed boards were held up with forged iron plates. This technique originated in France. Columns, profile cornices, arcades appear in late Romanesque furniture.

Gothic style (1200-1520), an important stage in the history of the development of furniture styles, the heyday of trade and crafts. In France, a new movement began from the Île de France in the north and continued from 1200 to 1525. It gave birth to a furniture style that existed for more than 300 years and entered the history of culture under the name of the Gothic style (Gothic).

The furniture is made of dark shades of wood, has many different elements. Oak, walnut, pine, cedar are variants of trees that are used for production. Such furniture is famous for its precise forms, extraordinary patterns. This direction originated in the XII century, which is why this style is reminiscent of the Middle Ages, and the furniture creates a sense of personal presence in those times. In such models there is upholstery on all upholstered furniture.

1-fig. Romanesque medieval furniture

2-fig. Monumental gothic carved walnut fireplace

Baroque the Italian word “barocco”, which is the name of the style, means a shell of an elaborate shape. Born at the end of the 16th century, the Baroque, in essence, was a direct, natural continuation of the Renaissance style.

The Baroque style in furniture with its magnificent forms was used to decorate the palaces and houses of the monarchy and the aristocracy. In creating rich furniture interiors, Italian masters knew no equal. Wealth and sophistication - this is how you can characterize this style, the main focus of this decor is on luxurious gilded furniture, which has rounded contours.

3-fig. Baroque furniture

On armchairs and chairs with carved backs, wardrobes, beds, there are refined curved patterns. Today, many buyers choose furniture of this style, because its cost is very affordable, and the luxurious and rich look has not disappeared anywhere.

Empire. The essence of the Empire style is already expressed in its very name: Empire – from the French "empire", empire. The first emperor of France sought to surround himself with splendor and splendor, which once surrounded the Roman emperors. Empire soon spread throughout Europe.

This is an imperial furniture style that originated in ancient France, and accessories in appearance resemble antique style. The main material for manufacturing is mahogany. Everywhere there are gold-plated ornaments, bronze decorative overlays. The color scheme is white with gilding.

4-fig. Empire style furniture

Provence. This is a light southern French style, which still pleases many connoisseurs of light, it displays the simplicity and at the same time the power of old French manors. As in all other styles, the main material used to make furniture is wood. Furniture in such an interior is characterized by an abundance of light and warm, natural shades.

Contemporary styles of furniture. The fast pace of life and technological progress have left a serious imprint on new styles of furniture. Modernity began to dictate new conditions, accordingly, there was a need to optimize the area of housing and the relevance of using all the free space. There are such main types of modern styles:

- modern;
- minimalism;
- high tech;
- constructivism.

Modern. Wavy, curving lines are the main features of this style, furniture made in exquisite colors, made of wood or forged metal, the characteristic of the style is glass, stained glass, artificial materials.

In Art Nouveau furniture, two lines developed in parallel; decorative - floral ornament of chairs and armchairs, cabinets glazed with curved glass, coasters resembling a cup of a flower in shape and constructive – characteristic of German and English Art Nouveau furniture products, straightforwardness and clarity of construction.

5-fig. Art Nouveau furniture

Minimalism. Simplicity and conciseness are the main features of furniture design in this style. The main task of this style is to create a feeling of free space, so all elements are minimally equipped with decor.

High tech. The most technological style of furniture design, sliding, built-in wardrobes, transforming sofas prevail. Products with a glossy surface, in most cases silver, complemented by bright colors and flowers.

Constructivism. The use of functional furniture is the main message of this furniture style, and black, gray, green and red colors predominate in production.

Thus, we can say that the modern abundance of furniture styles will allow anyone to furnish a house or apartment for every taste, you must also always remember that you can dream up, make an experiment, and then you yourself will be proud of your creation. A fresh and original look at the interior plays an important role in creating a special style in the room.

The study of furniture styles gives us an idea of the features of different eras, morals and customs. Getting acquainted with different styles of furniture of certain periods, we get an idea of their development.

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